

The role of geomorphometric predictors in LUCC modeling

Adam Rusinko, Jozef Minár

Department of Physical Geography and Geoinformatics
Comenius University in Bratislava, Slovakia

adam.rusinko@uniba.sk

Abstract—An adequate choice of independent variables poses a basal step to create successful model of Land-Use and Land-Cover Change (LUCC). Spatial predictors derived from digital elevation model (DEM) are a big group of determinants that are relatively easy to obtain. However, the review of more than one hundred articles showed that only basic geomorphometric variables: elevation, slope, partly aspect and characteristics of solar radiation are mostly used. In this study, 21 geomorphometric predictors are tested in LUCC models of 5 distinct changes in Slovakia: urbanisation, intensification, extensification, afforestation, deforestation. The changes were obtained from CORINE Land Cover (CLC) database in the period 1990 – 2018. Logistic regression was used to quantify the association of the predictors and LUCC. In the first step, the relationship of one variable to each change was investigated in univariate logistic regression models. Based on univariate models, insignificant predictors were removed from further analysis. The most important geomorphometric predictors identified by multiple-variable logistic regression models and hierarchical partitioning were elevation, slope, Casorati curvature, duration of solar radiation, relief amplitude, topographic wetness index, terrain ruggedness index, and relief brake force. All have a good energetic interpretation that could be important in land cover formation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Studies investigating Land-Use and Land-Cover Change (LUCC) are a common part of geo-science experiments and applications. Typical mapping of land cover classes and detecting changes over the years has gradually shifted to spatial modeling of it [1]. In general, the modeling of LUCC deals with very traditional geographical issue: the relationship between various geographical factors – spatial predictors and LUCC [2,3]. However, some data (predictors) are difficult to obtain (for example individual motivation of landowners [4]), another data have inappropriate spatial resolution. The modeling is therefore generally limited by availability of the input data [5]. In contrast of it, geomorphometric characteristics derived from digital elevation model (DEM) are a

group of spatial predictors that are easily obtainable, thanks to abundance of various, even global DEMs. However, the review of more than one hundred articles showed that most often only basic geomorphometric variables are used: elevation [6,7], slope [8], partly aspect [7,9], and characteristics of solar radiation [6,7]. Resulting from the classification of the fundamental geomorphometric characteristics [10] we assume that there are other geomorphometric characteristics which also could be relevant in LUCC modeling. Moreover, the theory of physical geomorphometry [11] supports better interpretation of these relationships considering the effect of gravitational force on the land surface processes.

Our aims were to: (1) review research articles and find the most used geomorphometric characteristics used in LUCC models, (2) systematically create the (exhaustive) list of potential geomorphometric predictors, (3) test several geomorphometric predictors in modeling of changes in the area of Slovakia from 1990 – 2018 using logistic regression, (4) find the most important individual variables and quantify their contribution in multiple-variable model with other non-terrain variables which play relevant role in LUCC modeling.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

A. Literature review

We searched for LUCC modeling studies in scientific databases (WoS, Scopus, etc.) using keywords such as LUCC modeling, geomorphometric characteristics, topographic variables and we tried to find this information in the articles: DEM product and its spatial resolution, geomorphometric variables derived from it, formulas and tools used in the calculations. Finally, we gathered one hundred LUCC and we made the list of the most frequent geomorphometric predictors used in LUCC modeling (Tab. 1).

TABLE I. THE MOST USED GEOMORPHOMETRIC PREDICTORS IN LUCC MODELING

Variable	Count
Slope	92
Elevation	83
Aspect	36
Solar radiation ^a	20
Topographic Wetness Index	9
Landforms ^a	8
Curvatures ^a	5
Topographic Position Index	5
Relief amplitude	4
Specific Catchment Area	4
Terrain Ruggedness Index	2
Drainage density	1
Stream Power Index	1

B. LUCC data

Land cover data were obtained from the official CLC dataset for the area of Slovakia. We used data from years 1990, 2000, 2006, 2012, 2018. Changes between 1990 and 2018 were identified by merging the partial layers of change. The changes were categorised by a diagram of land cover flows into six categories [12]: urbanisation, agricultural intensification, agricultural extensification, afforestation, deforestation, and water bodies construction. However, water bodies construction was excluded from the next statistical analysis because of the small area of change.

C. Geomorphometric predictors

Based on our prior knowledge and experience with geomorphometric characteristics, we derived 21 predictors from national DEM (DMR 3.5) with spatial resolution of 10m (Tab. 2). Firstly, we used fundamental local point-based variables, elevation and its changes (first and second derivatives) in the direction of the gravitational field introduced by [13,14]. In addition to basic trio of gravity-specific curvatures [15], field-invariant curvatures [16] (mean, Gaussian, Casorati) were also added. Local area-based variables were represented by relief (amplitude of topographic wave) ‘ra’, drainage density ‘dd’ representing length of the wave, and ratio of the wave amplitude and length determining relief brake force ‘rbf’ [17,18]. Secondly, we calculated characteristics of solar radiation. Thirdly, we added some variables, mostly various terrain indices, which are used in different geo-applications such as hydrology, geomorphology, etc.

TABLE II. LIST OF TESTED GEOMORPHOMETRIC PREDICTORS

Abbrev.	Variable	Notes on tools and sources
<u>elev</u>	Elevation above sea level	10m DEM
<u>slop_deg</u>	Slope [°, %, rad, sine, tan]	<i>Slope tool</i> ArcGIS Pro
asp	Aspect Sine of aspect Cosine of aspect	<i>Aspect tool</i> ArcGIS Pro
prof_curv	Normal slope line curvature	<i>Surface Parameters tool</i> ArcGIS Pro Enhanced GIS tools proposed by [15]
tang_curv	Normal contour curvature	
torsion_curv	Contour geodesic torsion	
mean_curv	Mean curvature	
<u>caso_curv</u>	<u>Casorati curvature</u>	
gauss_curv	Gaussian curvature	
<u>ra</u>	<u>Relief amplitude</u>	circle, r = 1500m
dd	Drainage density	circle, r = 1500m
solar_glob	Global radiation	<i>Area Solar Radiation tool</i> ArcGIS Pro
solar_dir	Direct radiation	
<u>solar_dur</u>	<u>Duration of direct radiation</u>	
a	Specific catchment area	<i>Raster Calculator</i> [19]
<u>twi</u>	<u>Topographic Wetness Index</u>	<i>Raster Calculator</i> [20]
tpi	Topographic Position Index	<i>Land Facet Corridor tools</i> – Extension for ArcGIS [21]
<u>tri</u>	<u>Terrain Ruggedness Index</u>	<i>TRI tool</i> SAGA GIS [22]
spi	Stream Power Index	<i>SPI tool</i> SAGA GIS [23]
mnrn	Melton Ruggedness Number	<i>MRN tool</i> SAGA GIS [24,25]
<u>rbf</u>	<u>Relief Brake Force</u>	<i>Raster Calculator</i> [17,18]

a. Underlined variables recorded the highest overall AUC in univariate regression models.

D. Statistical analysis

We used a regular sampling grid in square net with step of 500m. Values of changes and spatial predictors were assigned to each point of the grid. Univariate logistic regression models revealed eight geomorphometric variables, which are potentially significant for land cover changes in Slovakia (underlined variables in Tab. 2). AUC of ROC curve was used as the indicator of the model’s explanatory power. These eight predictors were subsequently added to the multiple-variable model, together with other spatial predictors which play important role in LUCC modeling: mean annual temperature interpolated to 100m grid (temp) from Climate Atlas of Slovakia [26], Euclidean distance to the nearest settlement (dist), and population density (pop_dens) at municipal level [27]. We selected multiple-variable models for the next analyses using the stepwise regression procedure. In each step, the variable with the lowest significance ($p < 0.05$) was

excluded from the next step of the procedure until each variable was significant. Lastly, we used hierarchical partitioning as a method for quantifying an individual contribution of the predictors to the overall variance explained by the model [28].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Resulting from univariate models, the highest AUC was reached by: ‘tri’, ‘ra’, ‘rbf’, slope, elevation, duration of solar radiation, Casorati curvature, and ‘twi’. These variables were used in multiple-variable logistic regression models (Fig. 1).

The explanatory power (AUC) of the models was relatively high for each land cover change, except deforestation: urbanisation 0.81, intensification 0.77, extensification 0.74, afforestation 0.80, and deforestation 0.66. However, the final pool of significant predictors was different for different land cover changes. Individual contribution of variables to the model explanatory power (sum of individual contributions = 100%) was calculated only for the strongest predictors after backward stepwise regression (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. AUC (ROC curve) of the multiple-variable logistic regression models of the land cover changes and independent contribution [%] of single predictors to models’ explanatory power.

Relative high importance of Casorati curvature (intensification – 17.26%, urbanisation – 13.79%, afforestation – 9.27%) is the most surprising discovery. This curvature is generally used only

occasionally, and our review indicates that has never been tested as a predictor in LUCC modeling. It is a measure of general surface non-linearity [15], expressing integral potential energy of surface curvature related to general landforms instability [11]. Investigation of possible relationship between physical specificity of Casorati curvature and its fruitfulness in LUCC modeling is a challenge for the future work.

Another non-trivial result is relative importance of two characteristics describing undulation of topography. ‘Ra’ (wave amplitude) and ‘rbf’ (ratio of wave amplitude and length) contributed to explain the model of afforestation (ra – 13.55%, rbf – 9.49%), and extensification (ra – 6.79%, rbf – 6.30%). ‘Rbf’ recorded almost the highest contribution in the model of intensification (19.34%), together with slope (19.58%). However, it is needed to be aware of parallel use of ‘ra’ and ‘rbf’, because of their mutual correlation. If the window for calculation has size of topographic grain, then ‘rbf’ integrates both, ‘ra’ and ‘dd’ (inverted value of wave length). Multiplication of ‘ra’ and ‘dd’ approximates ‘rbf’ and expresses the average slope of an area [17,18], that is measure of barrier effect of the topography or its brake force.

Positional geomorphometric variables as ‘tpi’ and ‘tri’ are measures of regional difference of potential gravity energy [11] that could also affect the land cover formation. It could be indicated by ‘tri’ with strong result in the model of urbanisation (36.22%) and weaker contribution of deforestation (6.79%).

The last unexpected result is relative importance of duration of solar radiation (intensification – 14.84%, urbanisation – 9.56%, afforestation – 6.27%). It does not use to be used in LUCC modeling, and solar radiation is often represented by global or direct radiation which showed low relevance in our univariate models. Similar to ‘rbf’, also solar radiation can be considered as a combination of another characteristics. In this case, slope and aspect. So, it might express their mutual effect on changes. On the other hand, the commonly used aspect parameter was not important in our analysis.

Non-morphometric predictors (pop_dens, dist, temp), held their stable position in the design of LUCC models. However, geomorphometric characteristics were more important. There are also cases (extensification and deforestation) where elevation and ‘temp’ had high individual contributions. It is well known that in mountainous countries (Slovakia), elevation can be used as a proxy for climatic characteristics [7], however elevation include also influence of gravity energy distribution. It can be a reason of its high individual acquisition to LUCC modeling in these cases.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study tested 21 geomorphometric predictors in logistic regression models. Preliminary results (univariate models) revealed the most significant variables: ‘tri’, ‘ra’, ‘rbf’, slope,

elevation, ‘solar_dur’, Casorati curvature, and ‘twi’. Result of traditional variables as elevation or slope is not surprising but success of some newly used variables is very interesting and physically interpretable. Casorati curvature as a measure of energetic disequilibrium of land surface [11]. Relative importance of wave characteristics: ‘rbf’ and ‘ra’ representing regional barrier effect of topography. Priority of duration of solar radiation over global/direct radiation. And notable result of ‘tri’ as a variable of (topographic) position and regional difference of gravity energy. Further research is needed to verify these results. An unsolved question is still the impact of DEM generalisation and changes in the size of computation window and sensitivity of land cover change to such technicalities.

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